

First record of the African wandering spider *Afroneutria erythrochelis* (Simon, 1877) from South Africa (Araneae: Ctenidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Afroneutria* Polotow & Jocqué, 2015 a relatively recently established African genus and the species *Afroneutria erythrochelis* (Simon, 1877) has a wide distribution throughout the Afrotropical Region but still unknown from South Africa. The male was described from Landana in Angola as *Phoneutria erythrochelis* and the first female from Chinchoxo, Angola as *Phoneutria auricularis*. In the present paper the species is for the first time reported from South Africa.

Keywords: distribution, biodiversity, new record, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large areas in South Africa were surveyed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and numerous Ctenidae specimens have been collected. The family is composed of small to large spiders that occur world-wide and are presently known from 40 genera and 490 species (World Spider Catalog, 2025). The South African Ctenidae fauna has not yet been revised, and known species are placed in the genus *Ctenus* Walckenaer, 1805 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022).

Afroneutria Polotow & Jocqué, 2015 a relatively recently established African genus is known from six species with *A. velox* (Blackwall, 1865) as the type species. One of the species, *A. erythrochelis* (Simon, 1877), has a wide distribution throughout the Afrotropical Region. It was also recorded from Namibia and Zimbabwe but was unknown from South Africa. The holotype male was described from Landana in Angola as *Phoneutria erythrochelis* and the female *Phoneutria auricularis* Karsch, 1879 was added from Chinchoxo, Angola.

The species is here newly identified from South Africa from material sampled during SANSA surveys in the Limpopo Province. Some additional records were reported from iNaturalist. We provide the new distribution records for the species, as well as images of live specimens with notes about its behaviour.

TAXONOMY

Afroneutria erythrochelis (Simon, 1877)

Phoneutria erythrochelis Simon, 1877: 222 (m)

Phoneutria auricularis Karsch, 1879: 347 (mf)

Ctenus erythrochelis Simon, 1897: 107; Arts, 1912: 188 (Syn of *Ctenus carsoni*, *C. johnstoni* and *Phoneutria auricularis*); Lessert, 1915: 44; Benoit, 1977: 698 (Syn of *Ctenus aurepubescens*)

Ctenus johnstoni F.O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1898: 21

Ctenus carsoni F.O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1898: 24

Ctenus aureopubescens Strand, 1906: 82

Afroneutria erythrochelis Polotow & Jocqué, 2015: 12 (mf, T from *Ctenus*); Sherwood, 2025: 125

Figures 1–3. *Afroneutria erythrochelis* female from Lephalale, dorsal, lateral and anterior views. Credit: Peter Webb.

Figures 4–9. *Afroneutria erythrochelis*. 4–5. Female epigyne. 6–7. Female habitus dorsal and ventral view. 8. Male palp. 9. Male dorsal view. Credits: 4 & 8. After Polotow & Jocqué (2015). 5–7 & 9. Peter Webb.

Diagnostic characteristics: The species has the ctenid eye pattern 2-4-2, with anterior and posterior row recurved in dorsal view (Figs 3 & 10). Leg formula 1423. Male (Figs 10–12): TL 29–30 mm. Carapace with broad dark irregular median bands. Abdomen with dense hair cover with faint paired markings (Fig. 9). Legs covered by long, golden hairs (Figs 10–11). Palp cymbium elongated, almost as long as tibia; conductor rectangular, curved; median apophysis drop-shaped, curved at base (Fig. 8). Female (Figs 1–3): TL 32.00 mm. Carapace with broad dark irregular median bands (Fig. 6). Abdomen with hair covered with dark paired markings; sternum dark as well as half of coxae. Legs covered by short hair and scattered dark setae (Fig. 3). Epigynum: triangular median field and short lateral projections of lateral fields (Figs 4–5).

BEHAVIOUR

Ctenids are ambush predators that do not build webs to catch prey. Instead, they roam forest floors, leaf litter, and vegetation, especially at night, using speed and stealth to capture insects and small vertebrates. Members of *Afroneutria*, like other ctenids, are cursorial hunters, likely active at night and found in forest litter or low vegetation. Sherwood (2025) reported on a specimen found in bananas that was imported from Kenya to the United Kingdom.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Burundi, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ghana, Gabon, Kenya, Malawi, Namibia, Rwanda, Tanzania, Zimbabwe and South Africa (new).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: (Fig. 13). *Afroneutria erythrochelis* is so far only recorded from three localities in the Limpopo Province mainly from the Savanna biome.

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Figures 10–12. *Afroneutria erythrochelis* male from Lephahlale, anterior and dorsal view. Credit: Peter Webb.

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